

BUCKLING OF EXTERNAL PRESSURE MIXED FIBRE CYLINDRICAL SHELL AND OPTIMUM PARAMETERS

Xie Yujun, Liu Zhanmin, Xie Genshuan
Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Fushun Petroleum Institute
Fushun, CHINA

ABSTRACT

The theoretical formulas of optimum parameters for the buckling of external pressure mixed filament-wound orthotropic cylindrical shell are given. The conditions are discussed in which the formulas may be used. Examples in this paper show that the formulas can be used not only to determine the optimum parameters under which the mixed filament-wound orthotropic cylindrical shell would acquire the extreme value of critical pressure, but also to find out the optimum fibre volume fraction of fibre hoop reinforced aluminum shell.

Keywords : Cylindrical shell, Mixed fibre, Optimum parameter, Critical pressure.

1. STRUCTURE OF FILAMENT-WOUND SHELL AND MODULUS

The model of mixed filament-wound cylindrical shell is shown in Figure 1. It is supposed to be piled up by $2n$ units, each of which is composed of three plies with different thickness. The thickness of each unit is t , and the thicknesses of the three plies are $t_{\gamma+\varphi}$, t_{γ} , $t_{\gamma-\varphi}$ respectively. So the model can be regarded as a multi-ply symmetric cylindrical shell.

If the unidirectional composites in ply orientation of $\gamma+\varphi$ and $\gamma-\varphi$ are the same but the unidirectional composites in ply orientation of γ is different, the cylindrical shell will be the mixed filament-wound structure. Its in-plane moduli are [1]

$$A_{ij}^0 = h(f_{\gamma+\varphi} Q_{ij}^{(\gamma+\varphi)} + f_{\gamma} Q_{ij}^{(\gamma)} + f_{\gamma-\varphi} Q_{ij}^{(\gamma-\varphi)}) \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (1)$$

where h is the thickness of the shell. If it remains constant and the unit number n is large enough (the multi-ply quasi-homogeneous laminate), its flexural moduli are

$$D_{ij}^0 = \frac{h^3}{12} (f_{\gamma+\varphi} Q_{ij}^{(\gamma+\varphi)} + f_{\gamma} Q_{ij}^{(\gamma)} + f_{\gamma-\varphi} Q_{ij}^{(\gamma-\varphi)}) \quad (i, j=1, 2, 6) \quad (2)$$

The $f_{\gamma+\varphi}$, f_{γ} , and $f_{\gamma-\varphi}$ in Equation 1 and 2 refer to the weighted factors which meet the equation of $f_{\gamma+\varphi} + f_{\gamma} + f_{\gamma-\varphi} = 1$. The normalized modulus of general laminates is the weighted sum of the off-axis modulus of plies in the unit. What we need to explain here is that Equation 2 is not inevitable and it depend on whether the number n of the unit is large enough. If n is infinit, Equation 2 is accurate. If n is finit but fairly large, Equation 2 appears in a approximate one. The example in paper [1] shows that when $n > 10$, the error caused by Equation 2 can be neglected and this is acceptable in engineering.

Figure 1. Model of the filament-wound shell. Because of symmetry only upper half of the shell is shown in (b). $t_{\gamma+\varphi} = f_{\gamma+\varphi} t$, $t_{\gamma} = f_{\gamma} t$, $t_{\gamma-\varphi} = f_{\gamma-\varphi} t$.

As $t_{\gamma+\varphi} = f_{\gamma+\varphi} t$, $t_{\gamma} = f_{\gamma} t$ and $t_{\gamma-\varphi} = f_{\gamma-\varphi} t$ shown in Figure 1, the geometric meaning of weighted factors is the ratio of thicknesses of plies composing the unit, i.e. $t_{\gamma+\varphi} : t_{\gamma} : t_{\gamma-\varphi} = f_{\gamma+\varphi} : f_{\gamma} : f_{\gamma-\varphi}$. Using the weighted factors, we can also determine the ratio of the fibre quantity in different orientations alone which the shell would be wound. If let $F_{\gamma+\varphi}$, F_{γ} , $F_{\gamma-\varphi}$ and $V_{\gamma+\varphi}$, V_{γ} , $V_{\gamma-\varphi}$ express the fibre quantity and the fibre volume fractions respectively in directions of $\gamma + \varphi$, γ , $\gamma - \varphi$, the following result may be obtained.

$$F_{\gamma+\varphi} : F_{\gamma} : F_{\gamma-\varphi} = (f_{\gamma+\varphi} V_{\gamma+\varphi}) : (f_{\gamma} V_{\gamma}) : (f_{\gamma-\varphi} V_{\gamma-\varphi}) \quad (3)$$

The weighted factor f_{γ} is now taken as a variable and let the factors $f_{\gamma} = s$, $f_{\gamma+\varphi} = f_{\gamma-\varphi} = (1-s)/2$. Each ply in the unit may be treated as the consisting of two oriented fibre of the same quantity. The two ply orientations of the fibre in each ply have the same magnitude but oppsite signs. The cylindrical shell becomes orthotropic. Then we have the following expressions of the normalized moduli of the orthotropic cylindrical shell varying with parameter γ , φ and s .

$$A_{11}^{0*} = s(U_1' + U_2' \cos 2\gamma + U_3' \cos 4\gamma) + (1-s)(U_1 + U_2 \cos 2\gamma \cos 2\varphi + U_3 \cos 4\gamma \cos 4\varphi) \quad (4, a)$$

$$A_{22}^{0*} = s(U_1' - U_2' \cos 2\gamma + U_3' \cos 4\gamma) + (1-s)(U_1 - U_2 \cos 2\gamma \cos 2\varphi + U_3 \cos 4\gamma \cos 4\varphi) \quad (4, b)$$

$$D_{22}^{0*} = A_{22}^{0*} \quad (4, c)$$

$$A_{12}^{0*} = s(U_4' - U_3' \cos 4\gamma) + (1-s)(U_4 - U_3 \cos 4\gamma \cos 4\varphi) \quad (4, d)$$

Where U_i' , U_i ($i=1, 2, 3, 4$) are modulus invariants of two different unidirectional materials in the unit.

2. CRITICAL PRESSURE

Based on experimental observation of the buckling models, classification of stress state and the order analysis, the simplified buckling equation of orthotropic cylindrical shell under the external pressure had been presented in paper [2], which is nearly as accurate as Donnell's. The critical pressure \bar{P}_{cr} for three typical boundary conditions (simply support at each end, clamped support at two ends, and simply support at one end and clamped support at the other) was given as follows.

$$\bar{P}_{cr} = \bar{K}_b \cdot \bar{K}_s \cdot \bar{K}_e \quad (5)$$

Where the constant factor \bar{K}_b is concerned with boundary condition, the \bar{K}_s is concerned with geometric structural parameters, and the factor \bar{K}_e is concerned with moduli of the cylindrical shell. The influence of boundary conditional factor, geometric structural factor and modulus factor upon the critical pressure is independent. And here \bar{K}_e can be expressed as

$$\bar{K}_e = \left[\frac{A_{11}^{0*} A_{22}^{0*} - (A_{12}^{0*})^2}{A_{22}^{0*}} \right]^{1/4} (D_{22}^{0*})^{3/4} \quad (6)$$

3. EXTREME VALUE ANALYSIS AND EXAMPLES

3.1 Extreme Value Analysis

From Equation 4 and 6, we can derive the relationship of factor \bar{K}_e and oriented angles γ , φ , weighted factor s .

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{K}_e = & \{ [s(U_1' + U_2' \cos 2\gamma + U_3' \cos 4\gamma) + (1-s)(U_1 + U_2 \cos 2\gamma \cos 2\varphi + U_3 \cos 4\gamma \cos 4\varphi)] \\ & \cdot [s(U_1' - U_2' \cos 2\gamma + U_3' \cos 4\gamma) + (1-s)(U_1 - U_2 \cos 2\gamma \cos 2\varphi + U_3 \cos 4\gamma \cos 4\varphi)] \\ & - [s(U_4' - U_3' \cos 4\gamma) + (1-s)(U_4 - U_3 \cos 4\gamma \cos 4\varphi)]^2 \}^{1/4} [s(U_1' - U_2' \cos 2\gamma + \\ & U_3' \cos 4\gamma) + (1-s)(U_1 - U_2 \cos 2\gamma \cos 2\varphi + U_3 \cos 4\gamma \cos 4\varphi)]^{1/2} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The extreme points of \bar{K}_e may be found from letting

$$\frac{\partial \bar{K}_e}{\partial \gamma} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \bar{K}_e}{\partial \varphi} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \bar{K}_e}{\partial s} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Neglecting small quantities, we obtain two group extreme points.

The first group extreme point:

$$\gamma_1 = 0, \quad \varphi_1 = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad s_1 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{2(Q'_{11}Q'_{22} - Q_{11}Q_{22}) - (Q'_{11}Q_{11} - Q'_{22}Q_{22})}{4(Q_{11} - Q'_{22})(Q'_{11} - Q_{22})} \quad (9)$$

Corresponding to this point, \bar{K}_e is

$$(\bar{K}_e)_1 = \frac{3^{3/4}}{4} \frac{(Q'_{11}Q_{11} - Q'_{22}Q_{22})}{(Q_{11} - Q'_{22})^{1/4}(Q'_{11} - Q_{22})^{3/4}} \quad (10)$$

The second group extreme point:

$$\gamma_2 = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad \varphi_2 = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad s_2 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{2(Q'_{11}Q'_{22} - Q_{11}Q_{22}) + (Q'_{11}Q_{11} - Q'_{22}Q_{22})}{4(Q_{11} - Q'_{22})(Q'_{11} - Q_{22})} \quad (11)$$

And correspondingly

$$(\bar{K}_e)_2 = \frac{3^{3/4}}{4} \frac{(Q'_{11}Q_{11} - Q'_{22}Q_{22})}{(Q'_{11} - Q_{22})^{1/4}(Q_{11} - Q'_{22})^{3/4}} \quad (12)$$

From Equation 9 to 12, it is not difficult to have

$$(\bar{K}_e)_{\max} = \begin{cases} (\bar{K}_e)_1, & Q_{11} + Q_{22} \geq Q'_{11} + Q'_{22} \\ (\bar{K}_e)_2, & Q_{11} + Q_{22} < Q'_{11} + Q'_{22} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

and the optimum parameters

$$(\gamma^*, \varphi^*, s^*) = \begin{cases} (\gamma_1, \varphi_1, s_1), & Q_{11} + Q_{22} \geq Q'_{11} + Q'_{22} \\ (\gamma_2, \varphi_2, s_2), & Q_{11} + Q_{22} < Q'_{11} + Q'_{22} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Since the weighted factor s^* is a limited value, i.e. $0 < s^* < 1$, the modulus components of the two unidirectional composites must meet the following equation.

$$Q'_{11}Q_{11} + 3Q'_{22}Q_{22} > \begin{cases} 4Q_{11}Q_{22}, & Q_{11} + Q_{22} \geq Q'_{11} + Q'_{22} \\ 4Q'_{11}Q'_{22}, & Q_{11} + Q_{22} < Q'_{11} + Q'_{22} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

So we can have $s_1 > 0$ in Equation 9, $s_2 < 1$ in Equation 11. It shows that Equation 15 defines the discriminant ensuring extreme points fall in effective region of the weighted factor.

When $Q'_{ij} = Q_{ij}$, i.e. the shell may be composed by the same unidirectional composites, Equation 9 and 10 will be equivalent to Equation 11 and 12. We have

$$\gamma^* = 0, \quad \varphi^* = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad s^* = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{4} \frac{Q_{11} + Q_{22}}{Q_{11} - Q_{22}} \quad (16)$$

and

$$(\bar{K}_e)_{\max} = \frac{3^{3/4}}{4} (Q_{11} + Q_{22}) \quad (17)$$

Equation 15 becomes $Q_{11} - 3Q_{22} > 0$. These results coincide with the ones in paper [3].

3.2 Examples

By utilizing Equation 3, 13 and 14, five examples to determine the optimum parameters, the factor $(\bar{K}_c)_{\max}$ and the ratio (expressed by R in table 1) of two kinds of the fibre quantity in longitude to in hoop for external pressure mixed filament-wound orthotropic cylindrical shell are given. The five examples, listed in table 1, may be divided into two classes. The first one, example 1, 2 and 3, is that we regard the unit to be composed of two different unidirectional composites, and find the extreme parameters. These three examples indicate that higher modulus fibre is always in hoop and lower modulus fibre in longitude for achieving maximum critical pressure, and the quantity of fibre in hoop is larger than that of in longitude. The second one, example 4 and 5, shows that the unit may be supposed to be composed of aluminum ply and fibre bundle ply, and the optimum parameters can be found. The meaning of parameter s^* in examples of the second class is the fibre volume fraction in the shell, which can be obtained only if the modulus of fibre is two times higher than that of the homogeneous material.

The relative curves of $\bar{K}_c(\gamma^*, \varphi^*, s) \sim s$ for these five examples, which reflect the influence of weighted factor upon the factor \bar{K}_c directly, are shown in Figure 2.

4. CONCLUSION

Formulas used to get optimum parameters, which makes the shell possess the maximum critical pressure, for external pressure mixed filament-wound orthotropic cylindrical shell have been given in this paper. Conditions in which these formulas may be used are discussed. A discriminant used to assess whether the cylindrical shell composed with some different unidirectional composites should obtain the extreme value of critical pressure is derived. It has the grave theoretical and practical significance.

The results of the five examples show that the formulas may be used to determine the optimum parameters for mixed fibre cylindrical shell and the optimum fibre volume fraction of fibre hoop reinforced aluminum shell.

Although the quantitative difference of moduli of the two unidirectional composites is manifest, the weighted factor s^* in the examples of the two classes are very close and the variation of $\bar{K}_c(\gamma^*, \varphi^*, s)$ in neighbourhood of s^* is quite gentle. So we would propose that the weighted factor for some composite materials may be regarded as a constant in engineering.

Table 1. List of original parameters and optimized results of the five examples.

No.	Type	γ ply			$\gamma \pm \varphi$ ply			optimum parameters (γ^*, φ^*, s^*)	$(\bar{K}_e)_{\max}$ (GPa)	R
		Q'_{11} (GPa)	Q'_{22} (GPa)	V_f	Q_{11} (GPa)	Q_{22} (GPa)	V_f			
1	Glass-Kevlar Epoxy	39.16	8.39	0.45	76.64	5.55	0.60	$(0, \frac{\pi}{2}, 0.157)$	41.96	1:7.16
2	Graphite-Kevlar Epoxy	181.80	10.34	0.70	76.64	5.55	0.60	$(\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}, 0.859)$	93.40	1:7.11
3	Boron-Graphite Epoxy	205.00	18.58	0.50	181.80	10.34	0.70	$(\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}, 0.822)$	123.88	1:3.30
4	Carbon-Al.	228.00	0.00	1.00	75.82	75.82	1.00	$(\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}, 0.625)$	109.16	62.5%*
5	Boron-Al.	400.00	0.00	1.00	75.82	75.82	1.00	$(\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}, 0.691)$	158.52	69.1%*

The modulus components of unidirectional composites come from [4].

* fibre volume fraction in fibre hoop reinforced aluminum shells.

Figure 2. The Curves of $\bar{K}_e(\gamma^*, \varphi^*, s) \sim s$ for five examples

References

1. Xie Yujun, Feng Guanzan, *Analysis and Calculation of Flexural Modulus for Symmetric Multiply Laminates*, Fibre Reinforced Plastics/Composites, No. 3, 1991, pp. 11-13.
2. He Yibo, *The Buckling of composite Fruncated conical Shells*. Doctoral Dissertation, Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics, 1990, pp. 33-36
3. Xie Yujun, Xie Genshuan, Feng guanzan, *Analysis of Optimal Stacking for Buckling of Symmetric Multiply Orthotropic Shell*, Proceeding of the 7th National Conference of Composite Materials, Dalian, China, June, 1992, pp. F-95.
4. Tsai, S. W., Hahn, H. T., *Introduction to Composite Materials*, Technomic Publishing Co., CT, USA., 1980, pp. 19-20.